

Use of Robotic Infrared Sensing Techniques for Social Distancing to Limit the Spread of Covid Pandemic

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Abstract: Restricting people ability to buy goods and services, beefing up border controls, and closing down public spaces are all examples of policies that have a chilling effect on economic growth and isolationism. Restricting access to public spaces is one example of such regulations. In this paper, we use smart Robotic Infrared Sensing Techniques the monitor the social distancing in smart cities. The study uses various Internet of Thing (IoT) devices as a wearable device to monitor the social distance. The simulation is conducted to test the efficacy of the Robotic Infrared Sensing Techniques than the existing methods.

Keywords

Monitoring; Social Distance; Robotic Infrared Sensing Techniques; Smart Cities

1. INTRODUCTION

The strategies that aim to reduce the amount of time and energy spent interacting with others are often characterised by the term social distance, which is often used to describe them [1-3]. Avoiding large groups of people, closing public buildings (including schools and offices), and keeping a safe distance from one another are all viable options [4] [5]. Disease transmission can be slowed by isolating people from their friends, who otherwise might have come into touch with an infected person [6] [7]. Methods of social isolation are most useful in the early phases of a pandemic, when they have the ability to slow the spread of the disease and delay its peak [8]. There will be less of a need for healthcare in general, and fewer deaths, as a result [9]-[12].

It was found that social isolation strategies could reduce the daily report count [13]. The burden on public healthcare facilities can be kept manageable by reducing the number of cases, and reducing social isolation is one of the most effective strategies to do so [14]. The number of people who are impacted can be reduced by social isolation [15].

Long-term consequences follow from instituting a class system at a young age [16]. Travel restrictions, closure of public areas, and public warnings to maintain a 1.5-2 metre distance from those outside

have all been imposed in various countries during the current COVID-19 outbreak [17-20]. Restricting travel, shutting off public areas, and warning the public to keep a distance of 1.5-2 metres once outside are all examples of these methods. However, it may be difficult or impossible to impose such thorough and rigorous laws because people will still need to travel outside for things like food, medical treatment, and job.

It important to recognise the role that technology plays in these contexts for facilitating social detachment processes. Its primary purpose is to detect and alert users when the distance between two nearby persons becomes so close that a collision is possible. Distancing strategies can be broken down into two broad groups: public and private. Closing or restricting access to schools and businesses, delaying or cancelling major events, and other similar actions are all included in this category. Border patrols and isolation wards are two examples of this type of safety precaution.

Individuals should be quarantined, isolated, and encouraged to maintain a safe distance from one another for their own protection [12]. The implementation of a social distance policy (such as lockdown at varying levels) in a country typically takes between thirteen and twenty-three days before it begins to have an effect [17, 18]. The second graph shows that the daily average of new cases starts to decline as social isolation becomes more common (i.e., the curve flattens). The best outcomes result from making strategic use of social distance, given its great potential.

Wearable internet-connected devices are used in this article to study the extent to which residents of smart cities interact with one another. Wearable Internet of Things (IoT) devices are used to quantify people psychological distance from one another in this study. To make sure the wearable technology will be more useful than current applications, a simulation is being run.

2. RELATED WORKS

Technology-assisted distance calculation for the purpose of secure aircraft boarding is an area that has seen extensive study [21]. In doing so, it exposed the inaccuracy and potential for injury introduced by the standard COVID-19 distance estimating approach. Because of these limitations, traditional tracking systems may not be applicable to the boarding and disembarking of passengers.

In order to identify distance-related violations, the researchers [22] developed a model. The paper describes a method for evaluating whether or not social distance standards have been broken in enclosed public spaces using an Internet of Things edge-based strategy centred on model transformation and a full-weighted graph.

This research [23] looked at the challenges of tracking and predicting MGs across international borders. In addition to providing information into which diseases are most likely to expand into the MG, etc., an integrated platform of this kind may aid in the early diagnosis of infectious disease issues of global significance.

The primary focus of the AI research was on enhancing predictive ability [24]. By tracking user vitals in real time, it can predict the onset of COVID-19 infection and immediately notify the user, their guardian, and any doctors or experts who are keeping tabs on the issue with an urgent alert, medical reports, and critical warnings.

Microcomputer modules were used in the creation of a system that students were given mobile hubs to use as identification, and the two were combined to provide a mechanism for measuring interpersonal distance on university campuses. The data is gathered by mobile nodes and sent to a centralised hub. The node has a neck strap so it can be worn there [25].

3. PROPOSED METHOD

While a Smartphone is required for some technologies (such touch tracing, Bluetooth-based systems, and Infrared-based systems), others (like temperature screening or distance tracking using a thermal camera) do not. Our classification system relies heavily on the tools used in earlier research. Components such as sensors and wireless networks are examples of such technology.

Some social distance systems rely solely on one technology (such as infrared to determine distance between two individuals) while others use a second, wireless technology (for example, to upload data for backup). Many different wireless and other technologies have been used in the past by social distance systems and scenarios. Personal area networks (PANs) and wireless local area networks (WLANs) like Infrared and Bluetooth have been

widely used in academic research on wireless and sensing technologies. Infrared networks are sometimes known as WLANs (wireless local area networks).

They focused a lot on Infrared in their research. By comparison, Infrared was treated as an afterthought in other research projects. Many researches, including those that made use of an internal navigation system, have relied heavily on Bluetooth technology. The use of ultra-wideband (UWB), radio-frequency identification (RFID), cellular, thermal, or infrared technologies as the principal focus of a study is unusual. The proposed model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed Model

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Among the most promising technologies, mobile phone use has the potential to lessen the negative effects of isolation. Those who have been quarantined or diagnosed with the disease can be monitored more easily. Many people have serious privacy concerns about the use of their location data for socially isolating practises which is discussed in Figure 2 and Figure3.

Figure 2: Wearable Device Performance

Figure 2: Network Performance

From these use cases, it appears that Ultra Wide Band (UWB) devices can be used successfully in both indoor and outdoor settings to socially separate individuals. Self-isolated people can have their movements tracked using other RF technologies, such as Infrared or cellular, to look for breaches of quarantine regulations. There is no need to set up any additional monitoring tools for this to work. If you have a Smartphone that supports UWB, like the iPhone 11 series, you can practise social distance even when you do not need location or navigation services.

Bluetooth technology could facilitate emotional detachment from others. User privacy must be maintained even if these services must provide reports to a variety of authorities and third parties. This could be a crucial area of study for stopping the spread of diseases and protecting people privacy. One drawback of utilising Bluetooth technology at a human scale is that localization techniques may lose precision if user devices are concealed in clothing or backpacks. For the technology to function successfully, electronic devices used by users must also be perpetually switched to Bluetooth mode. The integration of Bluetooth with other technologies to improve localization accuracy is another promising topic for study.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The primary goal of this study was to respond to inquiries on how to go about tracking down potential COVID-19 contacts. The findings of this research suggest that instead of using Bluetooth Low Energy-based smart phone apps for contact tracking, geolocation data from mobile users should be utilised (BLE). The proposed method for tracking contacts relies on the use of cellular networks and, by extension, the accessibility of received back-and-forth signals. However, there are certain downsides to this approach as well. To reiterate, cellular connections may be unreliable in areas with heavy RF signal interference, and they may not be

available at all in places like tunnels and the subway. Researchers did not have proper authorization to access user-provided data over the course of their study.

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